

Agronomy Career Influence Questionnaire

Demographics

1. What is your gender?

- a. Male
- b. Female

2. What year were you born?

- a.

3. Ethnicity

- a. White
- b. Asian
- c. Spanish, Hispanic, or Latino
- d. Black or African American
- e. American Indian or Alaska Native
- f. Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander
- g. Prefer not to answer
- h. Other (please specify below):

4. Income (Please exclude your spouse or partner)

- a. Not applicable
- b. Less than \$20,000
- c. \$20,000 up to \$40,000
- d. \$40,000 up to \$60,000
- e. \$60,000 up to \$80,000
- f. Greater than \$80,000
- g. Prefer not to answer

5. Employment Status

- a. Employed
- b. Unemployed
- c. Student
- d. Self-employed
- e. Stay at home
- f. Other (please specify below):

6. I grew up in a community with a population of:
 - a. <1,000
 - b. 1,000 < 2,500
 - c. 2,500 <50,000
 - d. >50,000

7. I currently live in a community with a population of:
 - a. <1,000
 - b. 1,000 < 2,500
 - c. 2,500 <50,000
 - d. >50,000

8. Highest degree earned
 - a. I did not attend college
 - b. Associate or technical school
 - c. Bachelor's
 - d. Master's
 - e. Doctorate

THIS NEXT SECTION ONLY APPLIES TO THOSE RAISED ON RURAL ACREAGE

9. I grew up working on the land that I lived on.
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

10. Growing up on acreage inspired me to choose an agronomy career.
 - a. Strongly disagree
 - b. Disagree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Agree
 - e. Strongly agree

11. Growing up on acreage is a necessary experience for an agronomy career.
 - a. Strongly disagree
 - b. Disagree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Agree
 - e. Strongly agree

12. My parents maintained a garden.
 - a. Strongly disagree
 - b. Disagree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Agree
 - e. Strongly agree

THIS NEXT SECTION ONLY APPLIES TO THOSE RAISED IN AN URBAN OR SUBURBAN ENVIRONMENT

1. I grew up with a job in the city.
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

2. Growing up in an urban environment inspired me to choose an agronomy career.
 - a. Strongly disagree
 - b. Disagree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Agree
 - e. Strongly agree

3. Students from urban environments have equal opportunities to choose an agronomy career.
 - a. Strongly disagree
 - b. Disagree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Agree
 - e. Strongly agree

4. My parents maintained a garden.
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

Job History

2. I had an agricultural job during my upbringing.
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

3. If you answered yes to the previous question, was this business was run by your family.
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

4. If you answered yes to the first question in this category, did having an agricultural job inspire you to choose a career in agronomy?
 - a. Strongly disagree
 - b. Disagree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Agree
 - e. Strongly agree

Does your current field of work involve agronomy?

- a. Yes
- b. No

Perception of supportive environment for pursuing a career in science

1. I like my career in agronomy.
 - a. Strongly disagree
 - b. Disagree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Agree
 - e. Strongly agree
2. My family was interested in the agronomy courses I took.
 - a. Strongly disagree
 - b. Disagree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Agree
 - e. Strongly agree
3. My family encouraged me to agronomy.
 - a. Strongly disagree
 - b. Disagree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Agree
 - e. Strongly agree

Interest in pursuing educational opportunities that would lead to a career in science

4. I majored in an area needed for a career in agronomy.
 - a. Strongly disagree
 - b. Disagree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Agree
 - e. Strongly agree
5. I have a successful professional career.
 - a. Strongly disagree
 - b. Disagree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Agree
 - e. Strongly agree
6. I make substantial scientific contributions.
 - a. Strongly disagree
 - b. Disagree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Agree
 - e. Strongly agree
7. When I tell others about my career, they respect me for doing scientific work.
 - a. Strongly disagree
 - b. Disagree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Agree
 - e. Strongly agree

Perceived importance of a career in science

8. A career in agronomy enables me to work with others in meaningful ways.
 - a. Strongly disagree
 - b. Disagree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Agree
 - e. Strongly agree
9. Agronomists make a meaningful difference in the world.
 - a. Strongly disagree
 - b. Disagree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Agree
 - e. Strongly agree
10. Having a career in agronomy is challenging.
 - a. Strongly disagree
 - b. Disagree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Agree
 - e. Strongly agree

How meaningful were the following aspects in influencing your career choice?

1. Interaction with peers in agronomy
 - a. Strongly disagree
 - b. Disagree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Agree
 - e. Strongly agree
2. Interaction with family in agronomy
 - a. Strongly disagree
 - b. Disagree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Agree
 - e. Strongly agree
3. Interaction with role models in science or agronomy
 - a. Strongly disagree
 - b. Disagree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Agree
 - e. Strongly agree
4. Interaction with teachers in science or agronomy
 - a. Strongly disagree
 - b. Disagree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Agree
 - e. Strongly agree

5. Interaction with college recruitment initiatives
 - a. Strongly disagree
 - b. Disagree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Agree
 - e. Strongly agree

6. Experiences in nature
 - a. Strongly disagree
 - b. Disagree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Agree
 - e. Strongly agree

7. Experiences with agriculture
 - a. Strongly disagree
 - b. Disagree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Agree
 - e. Strongly agree

8. The media (TV, magazines, documentaries, etc.)
 - a. Strongly disagree
 - b. Disagree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Agree
 - e. Strongly agree

9. Extra-curricular programs (FFA, Scouts, etc.)
 - a. Strongly disagree
 - b. Disagree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Agree
 - e. Strongly agree

10. Other (please specify)
 - a.

Stereotype Perceptions

1. Agronomy is a masculine career.
 - a. Strongly disagree
 - b. Disagree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Agree
 - e. Strongly agree

2. Agronomy requires physical labor.
 - a. Strongly disagree
 - b. Disagree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Agree
 - e. Strongly agree

3. Agronomy requires getting dirty.
 - a. Strongly disagree
 - b. Disagree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Agree
 - e. Strongly agree

4. Women have equal opportunities in agronomy.
 - a. Strongly disagree
 - b. Disagree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Agree
 - e. Strongly agree

5. People growing up in urban environments can excel in agronomy careers.
 - a. Strongly disagree
 - b. Disagree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Agree
 - e. Strongly agree

6. Media portrays agronomy as a masculine career.
 - a. Strongly disagree
 - b. Disagree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Agree
 - e. Strongly agree

How meaningful were the following sustainability aspects in influencing your career choice?

1. Food supply crises.
 - a. Strongly disagree
 - b. Disagree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Agree
 - e. Strongly agree

2. Water shortage.
 - a. Strongly disagree
 - b. Disagree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Agree
 - e. Strongly agree

3. Issues with conventional farming methods.
 - a. Strongly disagree
 - b. Disagree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Agree
 - e. Strongly agree

4. Media related to sustainability.
 - a. Strongly disagree
 - b. Disagree
 - c. Neither agree nor disagree
 - d. Agree
 - e. Strongly agree